

PERCEPTIONS AND EXPERIENCES OF ONLINE INTERNSHIP

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Conference Key Areas: *Industry and Companies liaison, regional Involvement and Innovation*

Keywords: *Internship, Online, Remote work, Industry liaison*

ABSTRACT

Remote working enables organisations to have location- and time-independent business processes. Working life practices should also be applied in higher education. Lapland University of Applied Sciences' ICT education in Finland met the challenge by developing an online internship concept that improves cooperation between the university and industry and promotes the content and quality of education. This paper describes the experiences of the research project of online internship models. Oral feedback from students (N = 12) and companies (N = 6)

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were analysed along with the online internship concept during 2021. The concept includes three types of process models. Based on the idea that business and industry representatives are active players in the process. The supervising teachers and technical support staff of Lapland University of Applied Sciences (UAS) acted as a support network. Results confirmed the notion of the usefulness and suitability of the concept for the purpose. The marketing of the concept was supported by a process website. The challenges found focused on, for example equipment resources and the pedagogical skills of industry representatives. The concept can be generalised regardless of the field.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Teleworking trends

Internships are an essential part of ICT engineering studies. Digitalisation and the proliferation of telework also call for a review of the professional training included in the studies. The COVID-19 pandemic changed the research design, such that constraints on gatherings and telework recommendations, as well as the response of companies to the former, increased the need to transfer student internships remotely.

In the statistics Finland 2018 Working Conditions Survey, 28% of employees said they work remotely and that 16% of jobs would have allowed them to work remotely, even if they did not do it for one reason or another. Moreover, 3% of employees said their employer did not allow telecommuting [1]. In other words, just over half (54%), or over a million employees, did not consider teleworking possible in their jobs in 2018. This was the response of most teachers, among others [1].

Telework has been exceptionally widespread in Finland during the COVID-19 pandemic, even on a European scale. It has been made possible by well-functioning telecommunications connections, a business structure that emphasises information work and, the fact that binding to the Finnish people alone has suited well.

During the great human experiment caused by the pandemic, about half of the Finnish employees as best worked remotely. In spring 2021, a further 42% were teleworking, of which 8% - including teachers - said they had worked remotely at some point during the pandemic [1].

Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, teleworking had become more common in Finland from 2013 to 2018, posting an increase of 12%. Growth certainly continued during 2019, with the digitalisation of working life accelerating the detachment of work from time and place. In five years the share of teleworkers has risen from 16% to 28% [1].

Educational institutions have begun to recognize the potential of virtual internships in gaining professional qualifications [2]. Virtuality offers organizations the opportunity to find talent globally and internationally [3]. It has been found that the advantages are the same whether the training is performed remotely or FTF (see e.g. [4]).

However, online internship poses challenges for project management and especially for the project manager [5].

1.2 The PracDis project

The PracDis (Practise at a Distance) project was launched at Lapland University of Applied Sciences, Finland, to improve cooperation between the university and companies by enabling remote internships for ICT companies. The project was implemented as a collaboration between ICT engineering and business information technology training. It was launched before the COVID-19 pandemic, but its importance was emphasised during the pandemic. The PracDis project developed a concept for distance learning that considers the perspectives and needs of both students and working life. It also expands the concept of internship to study work. This paper describes the latter part of the project, including the piloting results of the the developed concept. Its background study and concept construction are described in more detail in [6].

This publication is a continuation of a previously published study [6]. It presents experiences with the implementation of the concepts described in the previous work. The following sections describe the methodology and results of the survey. Finally, there are some reflections and recommendations for organisations that may want to try or apply the policies developed during the process.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Developing the concept

The study described in this paper is the second phase of a research in which the concept of an online internship model was developed. The first phase was presented in [6]. The concept was introduced in 2021 and the functionality of the models was piloted with industry and company, the results of which are reported in this paper. To clarify the methodology, the models are first presented in this section.

The concept includes three different models (Table 1) for location-independent internships depending on the student's personal use of time. It works both in the case of one student and as a team or project work implementation. The pilot studies were implemented in 2021 following the process models of the three concept models according to Table 1. A total of 6 business pilot studies were conducted, of which 5 were micro-enterprises and one large scale enterprise. Thresholds following Article 2 of the European Commission (2020) were applied to the classification of enterprises [7].

Table 1. Pilots and number of participants

Model of online internship concept	Description	Participants in pilot
Model A Online Internship: Individual format implementation	The student completes the internship as an individual within the credits specified in the curriculum for the internship	5 companies, 5 students (2 pilots interrupted)
Model B Extended Online Internship: Individual or project format implementation	In addition to the credits allocated to the internship, the student also completes the studies of the professional subject according to their requirements.	1 company, 3 students
Model C Academy Model: Project format implementation	The student completes the professional subjects according to the curriculum during the semester. The student team is disconnected from the regular tuition and timetable for the semester.	2 companies, 5 students

The process for model C is shown in Figures 1, 2, and 3. Figure 1 illustrates the process for the starting phase of model C, in which the student team and industry representatives work together to develop plans to complete the project with the goals of both parties in mind. Communication and documentation take place on a common teamwork platform, such as MS Teams.

Fig. 1. Process model of the starting phase [1]

In Figure 2, the project is carried out iteratively using agile methods such as Scrum [8]. In addition to the teamwork platform, version control tools and digital development tools are shared. Progress is regularly monitored through reviews. The university's technical support person and internship instructor will support project implementation and process when necessary.

Fig. 2. Process model of the implementation phase [6]

Figure 3 shows the closing phase of model C, which includes, in addition to the evaluation, a decision seminar or event in which, in addition to the summary, mutual feedback takes place. Furthermore, students are encouraged to create a demonstration, such as a video trailer, poster or brochure, that will be published on the organisation's page or another service for students to use as a reference in their job search. For the institution, it works, for instance as a merit for university industry cooperation.

Fig. 3. Process model of the closing phase [6]

The thoughts, expectations, and experiences of the students and the participating companies were collected throughout the process. The majority of feedback and experiences were received orally at the progress review or in the final seminar included in the processes. Students and company representatives were free to share their experiences, successes and failures, as well as ideas for developing concepts. A memorandum was prepared for each session, in which comments and suggestions for improvement were recorded. The contents of the memos were compiled into a single document and the material was analyzed using content analysis methods.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Model A

According to the feedback from the student concerning model A, the internship period went well and the employer was committed to the activity. Students perceived receiving enough information about the internship but had only a few situations where support from the institution was needed. They were particularly pleased to be able to complete the internship online, but some of them felt that their personal computers were not efficient enough for the purpose smooth editing videos requires a powerful graphics controller. thus, the availability of necessary equipment during the internship should be agreed upon with the employer.

According to the employer's representative, the internship likewise went well. Information was sufficient on how the internship was progressing, what was happening at each stage and what the goals were. The process models were clear to understand. According to the company representatives, students' adaption for online work proceeded smoothly. However, companies may not be able to act in online learning if they lack the understanding and ability to provide, lead and operate communication activities. The suggestion was that online working and communication should further consider an introduction and orientation phase for the industry representatives, for example, through a training package/information.

Two of the model A internship periods were interrupted for the students' reasons. In addition, the interruptions may have been affected by the initial challenge and lack of necessary support.

3.2 Model B

In the case of model B, students reported gaining more experience in project work, programming, taking responsibility and interaction skills. Their expertise also deepened, especially in considering the needs and requirements of the end-user. The students suggested that the educational institution and the companies should further increase their cooperation. Indeed, the pilot led to the recruitment of one student. The challenges mentioned were that the online support provided by the institution was not used at all during the pilot, though the possibilities for its use on

the team communication platform existed. The existence and importance of support and the institution's stakeholders must be further emphasised in the future.

3.3 Model C

The students and companies were also satisfied with the implementation and results of the pilot of model C. Students received positive feedback. There were no specific suggestions for improving the process. However, one company suggested that ICT education should pay even more attention to the security aspects and management in all courses. On the basis of the research results, the following areas for development will be examined in more detail in the further development of the model:

- Extent and coverage of initial orientation
- Deeper involvement of the company in the initial orientation
- More extensive presentation of tools and methods
- Clarity of objectives
- Increased number of reviews and feedback opportunities

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The online internship concept was piloted in six separate pilots by ICT students of Finnish UAS in cooperation with companies. Pilots followed the processes of all three models. Support was provided by the supervising teachers and selected technical support persons of the institution. Pilots were conducted using MS Teams as the team collaboration platform with all parties involved. The results of the pilots conducted were positive. Students and companies were satisfied with the process and the results, and no special development targets occurred. Some of the challenges focused on the equipment resources available for students and the online supervising capabilities of entrepreneurs.

To prevent interruptions, it is necessary to provide adequate support and guidance and ensure social contacts, especially in the initial stages. Model A is particularly sensitive to interruptions because the student works alone without peer support and a project team. In model C, the team support that comes with project formality can help the student. Lack of social contacts or threshold may prove to be a risk to model A. According to a Nordic study by real estate expert [9], the extended COVID-19 period has reduced the popularity of large-scale telework and partly taken away its benefits. The study also found that productivity initially increased, but the lack of social interaction began to feel heavy [9].

The role of companies in the concept is emphasised not only in the role of the substance expert but also in the roles of the employer, mentor, reviewer and motivator. Experienced employees in companies act as mentors to students. Company representatives have also been recruited as volunteer mentors for students [10], in which case, the company does not seek or achieve business added value.

Giving and receiving regular and constructive feedback promotes learning, increases motivation, and produces a positive learning experience [11]. Regular progress reviews provide regular feedback [12], allowing support needs to be identified and potential problem areas addressed early.

The introduction and generalisability of the concept under study in higher education depend on many factors. This particular concept is likely to be directly transferable or adaptable to educational cultures where teleworking and distance learning are already widely used in business. Additionally, cooperation between companies and universities in teaching or research should be strong so that cooperation at the level of organisations, especially individuals, works naturally. At best, distance learning can serve the common interests of business and higher education. A highly educated workforce is expected to integrate into companies and higher education institutions can leverage corporate knowledge and expertise, as well as update their teaching and research content. The results of the study are compatible with earlier publications [13].

This publication is a part of the PracDis project (2019 - 2021), which was funded by the European Social Fund, grant number S21814.

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